

VISUALIZED MODELING OF COMPO CASTING PROCESSING FOR MAGNESIUM ALLOY COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Visualized modeling using glycerin or water with clear vessel were performed in order to acquire the suitable compo-casting conditions for fabricating particle reinforced magnesium matrix composites with no pores and uniform distribution of the reinforcement in composite billet. The paddle type stirring blade and high viscosity of the matrix is suitable for the uniform distribution of the reinforcement in composite ingot because of optimum matrix flow. As gas bubble is difficult to release to the outside of the die if the matrix has high viscosity, so that Rheo cast process is suitable for the degradation of pores.

KEYWORDS: compo-casting, modeling, $Al_{18}B_4O_{33}$ particle, magnesium alloy, flow, microstructure

INTRODUCTION

Compo casting process is one of the representative composite fabrication techniques. This method is suitable for the fabrication of magnesium alloy matrix composites because of low combustibility and oxidation [1]. But there have some demerits. As many pores and inhomogeneous microstructure are introduced in the composites, it leads to the degradation of the mechanical properties and its reliability. In order to acquire the high performance composite, the homogeneous distribution of the reinforcement and the degradation of pores are needed. Unfortunately, the optimization of the fabrication conditions for composites is very difficult because the experimental analysis of the convection current for molten alloy during stirring process is difficult [2,3]. Consequently, the visualized modeling is desirable.

In this study, semi-solid magnesium alloy is assumed as the matrix and the effects of the fabrication conditions on pore and uniform microstructure in the composites fabricated by compo casting process were investigated by the visualized experiment using cylindrical clear vessel and clear solution. Then $Al_{18}B_4O_{33}$ particle reinforced AZ91D (Mg-9%Al-1%Zn) alloy composites were fabricated under the obtained conditions from visualized conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Fig. 1 shows the visualized model apparatus for compo casting. The apparatus consists of 60mm diameter cylindrical clear vessel fabricated by acrylic resin, stirring motor, torque meter and stirring blade. The configuration of stirring process was recorded by high-speed video camera. Glycerin and water were used for the matrix solution. Table 1 is physical properties of glycerin and AZ91D alloy. Density of glycerin and AZ91D is lighter than that of $Al_{18}B_4O_{33}$ ceramics. Differences in density between matrices (glycerin and AZ91D) and $Al_{18}B_4O_{33}$ ceramics are 1.74 and 1.19, respectively. As the wettability between the matrices and ceramics are 82 and 102 degrees, the values have some different. The viscosity of glycerin at 17°C is nearly equal to that of semi-solid AZ91D magnesium alloy at 580 °C, which fraction of solid in semi-solid condition is about 33%. The viscosity of water is nearly equal to the molten alloys. The solution was poured into the vessel and stirred by typical three blades, which forms paddle, propeller and pin types. Fig. 2 shows the shape and dimension of stirring blades. Paddle and propeller types make heavy convection in radial and axial directions, respectively. Pin type makes high shear strength for semi-solid matrix. The influence of the stirring condition, viscosity of the matrix, blade types, the height of the

solution in die and the distribution of the reinforcements in the composites were investigated. In order to investigate the flow of the matrix, methylene blue and glass beads with 3mm in average diameter was used for tracers. Then $Al_{18}B_4O_{33}$ particles / AZ91D magnesium alloy composites were fabricated under the results acquired from the visualized modeling. The effects of the distribution of reinforcement and microstructure were investigated by optical microscope.

Fig. 1 Model experimental apparatus of compo casting.

Fig. 2 Shape and dimension of stirring blade.

Table 1 Comparison of physical properties of glycerin and AZ91D alloy.

Materials	Density (Mg/m ³)	Wettability for $Al_{18}B_4O_{33}$ ceramics (degree)	Temperature at 2000 mPa·s in velocity (□)
Glycerin	1.264	82 (at 17□)	17
AZ91D	1.81	102 (at 630□)	580

Ref. Density of $Al_{18}B_4O_3$ is 3.0 Mg/m³

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to analyze the flow of the matrix solution during stirring in different blades, methylene blue injected as tracer in glycerin along the stirring axis. Fig 3 shows the appearance of visualized model using methylene blue and various blades. In paddle type, deep blue streamlines were observed in the spaces between the bottom of blade and the bottom of die and the part above the top of blade around the axis. On the other hand, methylene blue was distributed homogeneously in the space between top and bottom of blade. It seems that the flow of solutions is ideal in this space. In paddle and propeller types, streamlines were observed above the top of blade around the axis, but methylene blue did not spread over-all in die. It shows back flow to the axis is very strong. These flows are not suitable for the uniform microstructure in composites. This result shows the flow patterns using all blades are not suitable for the homogenous stirring and only paddle type blade is relatively good compared with other blades.

Fig. 4 shows the influence of height of glycerin in vessel and rotational speed of paddle type blade. Air was entrapped only under the condition of 70mm in height of glycerin and 500rpm in rotational blade speed. Liquid surface became hollow at the center of vessel and the blade engulfed the air directly. As increasing height of glycerin and decreasing rotational blade speed, the air trapping became to disappear.

The entrapped gas in solution is difficult to release to atmosphere because of high viscosity of glycerin. Fig. 5 shows the stirring configurations of water and glycerin using paddle type blade. The height of the matrix is 70mm (The distance between solution surface and the top of blade is 10mm.) and rotational speed of blade is 500rpm. Water and glycerin model show the molten (0%fs) and semi-solid (33%fs) conditions of AZ91D alloy, respectively. In water model, the center of solution surface concaved heavily and then outside gas was trapped in solution by blade. As the viscosity of water is very small, entrapped gas in solution was released easily. Although the deformation of glycerin surface is smaller than that of water, gas was trapped easily in glycerin and the entrapped gas is difficult to release to atmosphere

because of high viscosity of glycerin. Consequently, semi-solid condition is suitable for the prevention of the gas trapping.

Fig. 3 Appearance of visualized model using methylene blue. Methylene blue was injected in glycerin along the stirring axis. Blades are (a) paddle, (b) propeller and (c) pin types. The height of matrix is 70mm and rotational speed of blade is 500rpm.

Fig. 4 Influence of height of glycerin in vessel and rotational speed of paddle type blade. (a) 70mm and 400rpm, (b) 70mm and 500rpm and (c) 80mm and 500rpm.

Fig. 6 Appearance of gas bubble formation on glycerin after stirring

Fig. 7 Appearance (a) and schematic illustration (b) of visualized model using 10 vol.% $Al_{18}B_4O_{33}$ particles. Stirring conditions are 80mm in height of glycerin in vessel and 500rpm in

rotational speed.

Fig. 6 shows appearance of gas bubble formation on glycerin after stirring with 10 vol.% $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ particles. Many gas babbles were generated and grown at the solution surface. These babbles are caused by the trapping gas in as-received particles, that is, gas in gap between particles.

As pores in composites fabricated by compo casting are introduced by the trapping gas by stirring blade and in as-received particles, the optimization of suitable stirring conditions and adoption of Rheo cast process is suitable for degradation of pores.

Fig. 7 shows appearance and schematic illustration of visualized model using 10 vol.% $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ particles during stirring. There are three parts in vessel, which are mixing part of particle and glycerin (slurry part), penetration part of glycerin to reinforcement (high fraction part of particle volume, so-call, capillary part) and particle part. Mixture of particles and glycerin don't occur in capillary and particle parts because of high velocity and weak fluid flow. Consequently, it is desirable that bottom of blade approach to the bottom of vessel as close as possible.

Then, $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ particle reinforced AZ91D composites were fabricated under the condition acquired from the model experiment. Fig. 8 shows microstructures of composites fabricated under the condition of 0 and 33% in fraction of solid. The composite fabricated under the molten condition, that is 0% in fraction of solid, has a fine matrix structure and no pore, but the coalescence of the particles was observed. As low viscosity of the molten alloy has the low shear strength, it seems that coalesced particles cannot subdivide into fine. Otherwise, compo-casting composites has spheroidized and coalesced primary crystals with 100-200 μm in diameter. Particles swept out to post-liquid phase and coalesced particles were not observed.

In order to investigate the dispersion of reinforcement in composite ingot, the superficial fraction of reinforcements in various positions in ingot was measured. Fig. 9 show the relationship between superficial fraction of the reinforcements and each positions in the composites fabricated under the condition of 0, 20 and 33% in fraction of solid with $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ particles. In case of 0 and 20% in fraction of solid, the superficial fractions are relatively low in the middle in vertical direction and in the center in radial direction. In contrast, the difference of superficial fraction of reinforcements in each position was not observed in the composites fabricated under the condition of 33% in fraction of solid. Matrix having 33% in solid of fraction seems to have suitable velocity for the dispersion of the reinforcement.

Fig. 8 Microstructure of 10 vol.% $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ particle / AZ91D alloy composites fabricated using (a) molten (630 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) and (b) semisolid (580 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) alloy.

Fig. 9 Superficial fraction of the reinforcement in the composite bullet and positions of the composite. (a), (b) and (c) are fabricated under the condition of 0, 20 and 33 % in fraction of solid with $Al_{18}B_4O_{33}$ particle, respectively.

CONCLUSIONS

Suitable compo-casting fabrication conditions for $Al_{18}B_4O_{33}$ reinforced AZ91D composite was acquired from the visualized modeling using glycerin or water with clear vessel. Then the composites were fabricated under the condition obtained visualized modeling.

1) Flow pattern of paddle type blade is relatively good for the homogenous stirring compared with that of screw and pin type blades. Pores in composites are introduced from the trapping gas from stirring blade and the trapped gas in gaps in as-received coalesced particles. Rheo cast process and optimization of rotational speed, shape and set position of blade are important for the degradation of pores.

2) Compo-casting composites fabricated under the condition obtained visualized modeling has homogeneous microstructure with no pores and no coalesced particles. Especially, the condition of 33% in fraction of solid is good for uniform distribution of particles in ingot.

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